

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

D1.2

Fig. 01

Project:	PIE News – Poverty, Income, and Employment News (H2020-ICT-2015)
Duration:	1st July 2016 – 30th June 2019 (36 months)
Contract number:	Grant Agreement Number 687922
Partners:	University of Trento, Basic Income Network Italy, Centre for Peace Studies, Stichting STAFF, CREATE-NET, Stichting Dyne.org, Abertay University, Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute
Document Number:	D1.2
Contractual Date:	31/12/2016
Workpackage:	WP1
Distribution / Types:	PU
Version:	Final
Total Number of Pages:	29
File:	PIE_D1.2_FIN
Authors:	Chiara Bassetti, Giulia D'Alimonte

The Deliverable 1.2 is the Data Management Plan of the PIE News project. It aims at clarifying the procedures team members follow to collect, manage, and make publicly available the various types of data collected and generated through the project activities. It intends to provide team members with a complete guide on data management, with particular respect to privacy and data protection, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, to the Open Research Data pilot and how to make data F.A.I.R. Guidelines will be updated every time relevant changes in legislations or in the project development will arise.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fig. 02

The Deliverable 1.2 is part of the Work Package 1 “Project Management”. It provides guidelines, answers to issues, and presents the approach that the PIE News project team will adopt with respect to the management and protection of data coming from research involving human subjects. Legal and ethical issues related to research involving human subjects that entails the collecting and/or processing of personal data are identified and practically considered with respect to the PIE News project, also taking into consideration the different methods by which data are collected (interview, focus group, online survey, direct online retrieval, etc.).

Chapter 1 presents EU-level and national-based regulatory frameworks for potential issues that may arise in the conduction of the PIE News project with respect to data protection and management, and briefly touches upon issues connected to the Open Research Data (ORD) pilot to which the project participates. Chapter 2 presents the various datasets that the project will generate and describes, for each of them: data origin (and re-use when relevant); purpose of data collection with respect to the PIE News objectives; data types, formats and expected size; data utility and public availability. Procedures for data

collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction are better detailed in the Deliverable 6.5 – POPD – Requirement No. 5. Chapter 3 of this document describes the PIE News procedures for making data findable, openly accessible, interoperable and re-usable (F.A.I.R.), estimates the costs of such procedures, and identify responsible partners for data management. Chapter 4 deals with data security in terms of storage and transfer. Finally, Chapter 5 briefly considers ethical issues referring to the relevant ethics review and deliverables.

The intended audience for this deliverable is primarily constituted by the project partners, as the work contained in this document will support the implementation of PIE News. However, the research work conducted on the EU and national regulatory frameworks on privacy and data protection can be of interest for a wider audience (e.g., policy makers, researchers, the public).

An updated version of the Data Management Plan will be released if different data will be generated/collected, if changes in consortium policies or in consortium composition occur, and if any other external factor may affect the validity of the present DMP.

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

DATE	VERSION	AUTHOR	SUMMARY OF CHANGES
12/12/2016	V0.1	Chiara Bassetti, Giulia D'Alimonte	First draft
16/12/2016	V1.0	Chiara Bassetti, Giulia D'Alimonte	Minor changes; integrations to Sections 2.2, 2.3 and 3 after input by Fabio Antonelli, Stefano De Paoli, Mariacristina Sciannamblo
19/12/2016	V1.1	Chiara Bassetti, Giulia D'Alimonte	Revisions after internal review by Maurizio Teli; integrations to Section 2.1.1 after input by Stefano de Paoli
21/12/2016	V1.2	Chiara Bassetti, Giulia D'Alimonte	Revisions and integrations after internal review by Denis Roio
30/12/2016	Final	Chiara Bassetti	Final version with full adoption of VIGs

CONTRIBUTORS

FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	ORGANIZATION	CONTRIBUTION
Chiara	Bassetti	UNITN	Author
Giulia	D'Alimonte	UNITN	Author
Fabio	Antonelli	CN	Input for integrations to Section 2.3
Stefano	De Paoli	AU	Input for integrations to Sections 2.1.2, 2.2 and 3
Mariacristina	Sciannamblo	M-ITI	Input for integrations to Section 2.3.3
Maurizio	Teli	M-ITI	Internal review (comments)
Denis	Roio	DYNE	Internal review (comments and suggestions of integrations)
Daniela	Paes Leao	SF	Final visual formatting

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
API	Application programming interface
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
AU	Abertay University (United Kingdom)
AVI	Audio Video Interleave
BIN	Basic Income Network (Italy)
BY-NC-SA	Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC)
CC	Creative Commons
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CMS	Centre for Peace Studies (Croatia)
CN	Create-NET (Italy)
CNEL	National Council for Economy and Work
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DIVX	Digital Video Express
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DYNE	Stichting Dyne.org (the Netherlands)
EC	European Commission
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EU-SILC	European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions
EUROSTAT	Statistical office of the European Union
EUS	Early User Survey
F.A.I.R.	Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (data)
F/OSS	Free and Open Source Software
GA	Grant Agreement
GDF	Graph Data Format
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GNU GPL	GNU's Not Unix GNU General Public License
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol over Secure Socket Layer
ICTs	Information and Communications Technology
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
INPS	Italian social security institute
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISTAT	Italian National Institute for Statistics
ITU	International Telecommunication Union

JHA	Justice and Home Affairs (Office)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
M-ITI	Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute (Portugal)
M4V	Moving Picture Expert Group-4 (iTunes)
MARCXML	MAchine-Readable Cataloging XML
MISSOC	Mutual Information System on Social Protection
MKV	Matroska
MOV	QuickTime Movie
MP3	Moving Picture Expert Group-1/2 Audio Layer 3
MP4	Moving Picture Expert Group-4
MPEG	Moving Picture Expert Group
NC-SA-ND	NonCommercial-ShareAlike-NoDerivativeWorks (CC)
NDA	Network Dynamics Analysis
NGO	Non-governmental organization
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ODbL	Open Database License
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ORD	Open Research Data
PDF	Portable Document Format
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
SAV	Saved (file name extension SPSS)
SF	Stichting STAFF (the Netherlands)
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TC	Technical Coordinator
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UNITN	University of Trento (Italy)
USSS	User-Stakeholders Satisfaction Survey
VIGs	Visual Identity Guidelines
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WAV	Windows Wave
WMA	Windows Media Audio
WP	Workpackage
XLSX	Excel Microsoft Office Open XML Format Spreadsheet file
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	1
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY	3
CONTRIBUTORS	4
ACRONYMS	5
TABLE OF CONTENTS	7
LIST OF FIGURES	9
LIST OF TABLES	10
1. LEGAL FRAMEWORK	11
1.1 EU LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR PRIVACY, DATA PROTECTION AND SECURITY	11
1.2 NATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORKS	14
1.2.1 Italy	14
1.2.2 Croatia	14
1.2.3 The Netherlands	14
1.3 PIE NEWS APPROACH TO PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION	15
1.4 OPEN RESEARCH DATA (ORD) FRAMEWORK AND PIE NEWS APPROACH	16
2. PIE NEWS DATA	18
2.1 DESK RESEARCH AND RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA	18
2.1.1 Data origin	18
2.1.2 Data collection purposes and its relation to the PIE News objectives	19
2.1.3 Data types, formats, and expected size	19
2.1.4 Data utility and public availability	19
2.2 FACE-TO-FACE RESEARCH AND EVALUATION ACTIVITIES AT PILOT SITES	19
2.2.1 Data origin	19
2.2.2 Data collection purposes and its relation to the PIE News objectives	19
2.2.3 Data types, formats, and expected size	20
2.2.4 Data utility and public availability	20
2.3 ONLINE RESEARCH AND EVALUATION ACTIVITIES	20
2.3.1 Data origin	20
2.3.2 Data collection purposes and its relation to the PIE News objectives	20
2.3.3 Data types, formats, and expected size	21

2.3.4 Data utility and public availability.....	21
3. PIE NEWS F.A.I.R. DATA.....	22
3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE.....	23
3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE.....	24
3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE.....	25
3.4 INCREASING DATA RE-USE: LICENSES.....	25
3.5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES.....	25
4. DATA SECURITY.....	26
5. ETHICAL ASPECTS.....	28
REFERENCES.....	29

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
01	Zagreb Workshop	01
02	Zagreb Workshop	02
03	Zagreb Workshop	11
04	Zagreb Workshop	13
05	Zagreb Workshop	15
06	Zagreb Workshop	18
07	Zagreb Workshop	20
08	Zagreb Workshop	22
09	Zagreb Workshop	24
10	Zagreb Workshop	26
11	Zagreb Workshop	28

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE	TITLE	PAGE
1	Summary of data	22

1. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Fig. 03

The PIE News project aims at fostering the emergence of commonfare as an alternative economic model to fight poverty. The consortium will pursue this goal through a Collective Awareness Platform which (a) inform people about existing welfare state provisions, (b) provides them with the means to share good practices on how to handle poverty related issues, and (c) supports their abilities to network and sustain real-life value. To fulfil the objective, personal data protection and other legal issues are identified in this chapter.

Privacy and data protection are socio-technical issues relevant for software development projects and system design. They lead to requirements for the design of the technical infrastructure as well as for policies and agreements that have to be enforced on an organizational level. Data privacy is the right of any individual to expect that his/her personal information directly or indirectly collected are processed securely and are not disseminated without their written consent. Data privacy must not be subject to “mission creep”, i.e., information collected with permission for one purpose and used without permission for other reasons. Data protection is the framework of security measures designed to guarantee that data is handled in such a manner as to ensure that they are safe from unintended, unwanted or malevolent use. Data protection is the technical mechanism to ensure data privacy.

EU Directives generally do not directly apply in the EU countries and need to be nationally implemented by each country through laws and regulations. As countries have some freedom in the implementation of directives, stricter requirements than those prescribed by the directives may apply in certain EU countries. Furthermore, the national data protection legislation is, in many respects, complemented or overlapped by sector specific legislation that also needs to be considered. Therefore, to get a clear and comprehensive picture of the data protection requirements, it is essential to check the national frameworks, national data protection laws, unfair competition legislation, telecommunications laws and any other local data protection regulations.

1.1 EU LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR PRIVACY, DATA PROTECTION AND SECURITY

Privacy is enabled by protection of personal data. Under the European Union law, personal data is defined as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person” [1]. The collection, use and disclosure of personal data at a European level are regulated by the following directives and regulation:

- ▶ Directive 95/46/EC on protection of personal data (Data Protection Directive) [1]
- ▶ Directive 2002/58/EC on privacy and electronic communications (e-Privacy Directive) [2]
- ▶ Directive 2009/136/EC (Cookie Directive) [3]
- ▶ Regulation 2016/679/EC (repealing Directive 95/46/EC) [4]
- ▶ Directive 2016/680/EC [5]

According to the Regulation 2016/679/EC, **personal data**

means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (art. 4.1).

The same Directive also defines personal **data processing** as

any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination

or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction (art. 4.2).

There are several legal acts within the EU Law that address and regulate these issues:

▶ Charter of Fundamental rights of the EU:

Article 7 states that “everyone has the right respect for private and family life, home and communications”.

Article 8 regulates that “everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her” and that processing of such data must be “on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law”.

▶ Regulation 2016/679/EC regulates the processing of personal data regardless of whether such processing is automated or not. The principle is that personal data should not be processed at all, except when certain conditions are met.

- Article 5(b) states that personal data

shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes (“purpose limitation”).

- Article 6 defines criteria for making personal data processing legitimate:

- the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes;
- processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;
- processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject; processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;
- processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller;
- processing is necessary for the purposes of the

legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.

▶ Directive 2002/58/EC (Directive on privacy and electronic communications, also known as e-Privacy Directive) concerns the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector and deals with the regulation of several important issues such as confidentiality of information, treatment of traffic data, spam and cookies [2].

- Article 5 Confidentiality of the communications states:

1. Member States shall ensure the confidentiality of communications and the related traffic data by means of a public communications network and publicly available electronic communications services, through national legislation. Especially, they shall prohibit listening, tapping, storage or other kinds of interception or surveillance of communications and the related traffic data by persons other than users, without the consent of the users concerned, except when legally authorized to do so in accordance with Article 15(1). This paragraph shall not prevent technical storage which is necessary for the conveyance of a communication without prejudice to the principle of confidentiality.
2. Paragraph 1 shall not affect any legally authorized recording of communications and the related traffic data when carried out during lawful business practice to providing evidence of a commercial transaction or of any other business communication.
3. Member States shall ensure that the use of electronic communications networks to store information or to gain access to information stored in the terminal equipment of a subscriber or user is only allowed on condition that the subscriber or user concerned is provided with clear and comprehensive information in accordance with Directive 95/46/EC, inter alia about the purposes of the processing, and is offered the right to refuse such processing by the data controller. This shall not prevent any technical storage or access for the sole purpose of carrying out or facilitating the transmission of a communication over an electronic communications network, or as

strictly necessary to provide an information society service explicitly requested by the subscriber or user.

▶ Directive 2009/136/EC (Cookie Directive)

This Directive amended Directive 2002/58/EC, requiring end user consent to the storing of cookies on their computer. Cookies are hidden information exchanged between an Internet user and a web server stored in a file on the user's hard disc. They can be used to monitor Internet activities of the user [2].

Article 57 of the Directive states that security measures (referred to in Paragraph 1 Article 4 of the Directive 2002/58/EC) shall at least:

- ▶ ensure that personal data can be accessed only by authorised personnel for legally authorised purposes, and that the personal data stored or transmitted, as well as the network and services, are protected. Moreover, a security policy with respect to the processing of personal data should be established in order to identify vulnerabilities in the system, and monitoring and preventive, corrective and mitigating action should be regularly carried out.

Data should be secure from viruses, hacker attacks, forgery, etc. Security means protection of information and information systems by ensuring confidentiality, availability, integrity, authentication, and non-repudiation.

- ▶ Confidentiality: Information is not made available or disclosed to unauthorized individuals and entities.
- ▶ Availability: Data/information have to be available, only authorized persons can remove it, in accordance to law
- ▶ Integrity: only authorized persons can modify the data/information, in accordance to law
- ▶ Authentication must be preserved (data/information must be authentic)
- ▶ Non-repudiation - participants will not be able to successfully challenge the authorship of the data provided

The Directive 2002/58/EC (e-Privacy Directive), Article 4, also assess that:

1. The provider of a publicly available electronic communications service must take appropriate technical and organizational measures to safeguard security of its services, if necessary in conjunction with the provider of the public communications network with respect to network security. Having regard to the state of the art and the cost of their implementation, these measures shall ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk presented.
2. In case of a particular risk of a breach of the security of the network, the provider of a publicly available electronic communications service must inform the subscribers concerning such risk and, where the risk lies outside the scope of the measures to be taken by the service provider, of any possible remedies, including an indication of the likely costs involved.

Furthermore, the Council Framework Decision (2005/222/JHA on attacks against information systems) [6] addresses the most significant forms of criminal activity against information systems, such as hacking, viruses and denial of service attacks. The Framework Decision seeks to approximate criminal law across the EU to ensure that Europe's law enforcement and judicial authorities can take action against this form of crime.

Since 2013, the Directive 2013/40/EU on attacks against information systems [7] replaces the Council Framework Decision (2005/222/JHA); its aim is

to approximate the criminal law of the Member States in the area of attacks against information systems by establishing minimum rules concerning the definition of criminal offences and the relevant sanctions and to improve cooperation between competent authorities, including the police and other specialised law enforcement services of the Member States, as well as the competent specialised Union agencies and bodies, such as Eurojust, Europol and its European Cyber Crime Centre, and the European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA).

Fig. 04

1.2 NATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

1.2.1 Italy

In Italy protection of personal data is guaranteed by the Italian Legislative Decree 30 June 2003, n. 196, in compliance with the EU Law. The Law n. 547, 23th December 1993, defines the Criminal Code and the Criminal Procedure Code on the subject of computer crime.

The Decree 196/2003, art. 13, states that “the data subject as well as any entity from whom or which personal data are collected shall be preliminarily informed”; to this regard, the PIE News research team will inform participants and platform users’ about the aim of the project and will conduct activities only upon subjects’ **explicit informed consent** about data collection and processing, as detailed in the deliverables D6.3 – POPD - Requirement No. 3 and D6.7 – H - Requirement No. 7. If a subject revokes his/her consent,

data shall be a) destroyed; b) assigned to another data controller, provided they are intended for processing under terms that are compatible with the purposes for which the data have been collected; c) kept for exclusively personal purposes, without being intended for systematic communication or dissemination; or d) kept or assigned to another controller for historical, scientific or statistical purposes, in compliance with laws, regulations, Community legislation and the codes of conduct and professional practice adopted in pursuance of article 12.

Furthermore, the Decree explicitly limits the collection and the processing of **sensitive** data (art. 20), as these activities “shall only be allowed where it is expressly authorised by a law specifying the categories of data that may be processed and the categories of operation that may be performed as well as the substantial public interest pursued” as well as only upon data subjects’ consent.

A specific law (Legge Stanca, Art. 4, 9 January 2004) has been defined to face the issue of **accessibility**, intended as the “ability of computer systems, in the manner and to the extent permitted by technological knowledge, to provide services and usable information, without discrimination, even for those who, because of personal disabilities, require assistive technology or special configurations”.

1.2.2 Croatia

In Croatia, the protection of personal data is guaranteed by The Act on Personal Data Protection (Official Gazette of the Republic of Croatia, No. 103/03), the Amendments to the Act on Personal Data Protection (Official Gazette, No. 118/06, No. 41/08, No. 130/11), the Regulation on the method of maintaining records on personal data filing system and the form of such records (Official Gazette, No. 105/04), and the Regulation on the manner of storing and special measures of technical protection of the special categories of personal data (Official Gazette, No. 139/04). On-line privacy and cookies are regulated by the Electronic Communications Act

(Official Gazette, Nos. 73/2008, 90/2011, 133/2012, 80/2013 and 71/2014) which has implemented Directive 2002/58/EZ on personal data processing and privacy protection in electronic communications sector.

According to the Act, personal data can always be gathered “for a purpose known to the data subject” (artt. 6, 8); to this regard, the PIE News research team will inform participants and platform users’ about the aim of the project and will conduct activities only upon subjects’ explicit informed consent about data collection and processing, as detailed in the Deliverables 6.3 – POPD - Requirement No. 3 and D6.7 – H - Requirement No. 7. If a subject revokes his/her consent, data can still be processed for statistical purposes only when personal information can no longer lead to the identification of the person it relates to (art. 7).

For what concerns **sensitive data**, the Croatian Act is fully compliant with the EU regulation [4], as it prohibits any processing “to collect and subsequently process personal data pertaining to racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or other beliefs, trade union membership, health or sexual orientation, as well as personal data regarding criminal and misdemeanour proceedings” (art. 8). The same article specifies also that the collection and processing of sensitive data is not forbidden in so far this is carried out with the data subject’s explicit consent; however, as stated in the Deliverable 6.2 – POPD - Requirement No. 2, the PIE News research team will not collect sensitive data on purpose.

The Croatian Act explicitly states that “personal data processed for scientific research or statistical purposes must not allow for the identification of persons the personal data refers to” (art. 11); the PIE News research team will handle data collected in Croatia in compliance with the Croatian regulation by following the procedures described in this document and in the Deliverable 6.5 – POPD - Requirement No. 5: Data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction. The same procedures also guarantee data security as explicitly requested in article 18: “Personal data in personal data filing systems shall be adequately protected from accidental or deliberate abuse, destruction, loss, unauthorized alteration or access”.

1.2.3 The Netherlands

In Netherlands, the protection of personal data is guaranteed by the Dutch Personal Data Protection Act of 6 July 2000 and in force as at 1 January 2016, in compliance with the EU Law.

Among others criteria, the Act states that personal data can be processed only if “the data processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party to whom the data are disclosed, unless such interests are overridden by the interests or the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject, notably the right to privacy, which require protection” (Sect. 8, f), thus allowing the Dutch partners to conduct the PIE News activities while being the controllers of all data gathered in the Netherlands.

Furthermore, the Dutch Act allows the PIE News activities as it declares that “Further processing of the data for historical, statistical or scientific purposes is not considered incompatible if the controller has taken the measures necessary to ensure that the further processing is carried out solely for those specific purposes” (Sect. 9, 3).

In addition to EU regulations and the procedures described in this Deliverable as well as in the Deliverable 6.5 – POPD – Requirement No. 5: Data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction, the Dutch Act forces the controller of data to ensure that the processors “provides sufficient guarantees in respect of the technical security measures and organisational measures governing the processing to be carried out and in respect of the report of a breach of security” (Sect. 14, 1).

For what concerns **sensitive data**, the Dutch Act is completely compliant with the EU regulation [4], as it forbids any processing “of personal data relating to a person’s religion or belief, race, political affinity, health, sex life and trade union membership [...] The same applies to personal data concerning criminal law matters and personal data on unlawful or objectionable conduct in connection with a prohibition imposed in response to such conduct” (Sect. 16). In Section 23 the Act specifies that the processing of sensitive data is not forbidden in so far this is carried out with the data subject’s explicit consensus or for scientific purposes; however, as stated in the Deliverable 6.2 – POPD – Requirement No. 2, the PIE News research team will not collect sensitive data on purpose.

1.3 PIE NEWS APPROACH TO PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION

On the basis of the above described regulations, and with respect to the PIE News project, it is possible to define the following requirements in relation to privacy, data protection and security:

- ▶ **Minimization:** PIE News project must only handle minimal data (that is, the personal data that is effectively required for the conduction of the project) about participants.

- ▶ **Transparency:** the PIE News project will inform data subjects about which data will be stored, who these data will be transmitted to and for which purpose, and about locations in which data may be stored or processed.
- ▶ **Consent:** Consents have to be handled either paper-based or through the user interface, allowing the users to agree the transmission and storage of personal data. The consent text included in the interface must specify which data will be stored, who they will be transmitted to and for which purpose for the sake of transparency. An applicant, who does not provide this consent for data necessary for the participation process, will not be allowed to participate. The consent legal text must be customized, under the responsibility of each pilot partner, for each pilot country with references to the local legislation that applies.
- ▶ **Defaults:** By default, data must not be automatically shared. Data sharing and diffusion applies just to data for which consent has been given, and in accordance with the diffusion terms expressed by the consent.
- ▶ **Purpose specification and limitation:** personal data must be collected just for the specified purposes of the participation process and not further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes. Besides this, PIE News partners must ensure that personal data are not (illegally) processed for further purposes. So, the participants to pilot activities, and users when registering into the platform, have to receive a legal note specifying this.
- ▶ **Erasure of data:** personal data must be kept in a form that permits the identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data were collected or for which they are further processed. Personal data that are not necessary any more must be erased or truly anonymised. If this data cannot be erased due to legal retention rules (e.g., tax regulations), access to this personal data should be blocked. The PIE News members, and especially who is responsible for data storage (see Sect. 3.5), should ensure secure erasure.

Fig. 05

- ▶ **Anonymity:** The PIE News team must ensure anonymity by applying two strategies. On the one hand, anonymity will be granted through data generalisation and pseudonymisation; on the other hand, citizens' participation to the project platform will be anonymous except they voluntarily decide otherwise.
- ▶ **Accountability:** It shall be possible to establish what an entity did at a certain point in time in the past and how.
- ▶ **Cookies:** Cookies will be used in the case of users that agree to register to the PIE News platform and that have agreed to do it via informed consent procedure to allow the platform to track their behaviour offering them personalized services, as clearly stated in the platform registration terms and conditions. As for unregistered users, cookies will not be stored, thereby granting the possibility of fully anonymous navigation;
- ▶ **Security:** The protocol used for data exchange within the PIE News project must support encryption with SSL and TLS, which can be regarded as state-of-the-art encryption methods. Encryption of personal data must be used in all cases when "in transit" and when available to data "at rest". Remote administration of the platform will only take place via a secure communication channel.
- ▶ **Hosting of Data:** Data must be stored on secure repositories, and personal data can be accessed only by authorized staff, following authorization and security policies agreed with the whole project consortium (D1.1 – Project Handbook, Ch. 5), and in compliance with procedures described in this document (Ch. 4 "Data security") and in the Deliverable 6.5 – POPD – Requirement No. 5: Data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction, Sect. 1.2 and Sect. 1.3.

The above-mentioned requirements translate into three pillars within the PIE News project:

- ▶ **Confidentiality and anonymity** – Confidentiality will be guaranteed whenever possible. The only exemption can be in some cases for the researcher directly interacting with a group of participants (e.g., focus group). The PIE News research team will not make publicly accessible any personal data. Anonymity will be granted through generalization and pseudonymisation, on the one hand; on the other hand, only platform users will be able to voluntarily choose to disclose personal information (e.g., in their profile) on their own responsibility. Furthermore, provisions will be taken to avoid the possibility of information linkage. See also D1.1 – Project Handbook, Ch. 5.
- ▶ **Informed consent** – The informed consent policy requires that each participant will provide his/her informed consent prior to the start of any activity

involving him/her. All people involved in the PIE News face-to-face research and evaluation activities (interviews, focus groups, workshops) will be asked to read and sign an Informed Consent Form explaining how personal data will be collected, managed and stored. All platform users would be able to read the Terms of service; registered users will receive a dated copy of the same document via e-mail upon registration. See also D6.3 – POPD – Requirement No. 3: Informed consent, D6.7 – H – Requirement No. 7: Informed consent.

- ▶ **Circulation of the information limited to the minimum required** for processing and preparing the anonymous open data sets – To achieve a limited circulation of the information, the database containing in anonymous form the data collected from the users will be distributed to the partners, if needed at all, through protected and encrypted Internet connections; the raw data will only be shared if it is required for the development. The researchers will never pass on or publish the data without first protecting participants' identities. No irrelevant information will be collected; at all times, the gathering of private information will follow the principle of proportionality by which only the information strictly required to achieve the project objectives will be collected. In all cases, the right of data cancellation will allow all users to request the removal of their data from the project repository at any time.

1.4 OPEN RESEARCH DATA (ORD) FRAMEWORK AND PIE NEWS APPROACH

The PIE News project is part of the Horizon2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORD pilot) [8], that "aims to make the research data generated by selected Horizon 2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, while at the same time protecting sensitive data from inappropriate access"¹. This implies that the PIE News research team will deposit data on which research findings are based and/or data with a long-term value. Furthermore, Open Research Data will allow other scholars to carry on studies, hence fostering the general impact of the project itself. This approach to ORD is fostered also by the adoption of F/OSS (Free and Open Source Software) for various of the project activities, and especially for the PIE News platform, which will leverage exclusively on F/OSS. F/OSS contributes in making the research data widely and freely accessible as much as possible; it also help in preventing data misuse.

As the EC states, Research Data "refers to information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. [...] Users can normally access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate openly accessible research

¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/opendatapilot>

data free of charge” [9]. However, the ORD pilot does not force the research teams to share all the data. There is in fact a constant need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialization and Intellectual Property Rights (IRP), privacy concerns, and security.

For this reason, there is an opt-out option, which can apply to all, or a part of, the data. The option applies to the following cases:

- ▶ participation is incompatible with the obligation to protect results that can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited;
- ▶ participation is incompatible with the need for confidentiality in connection with security issues;
- ▶ participation is incompatible with rules on protecting personal data;
- ▶ participation would mean that the project’s main aim might not be achieved;
- ▶ the project will not generate / collect any research data or;
- ▶ there are other legitimate reasons [9].

The PIE News research team adopts the best practice the ORD pilot encourages – that is, “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Among the above-mentioned ones, cases a), d), e), and f) do not apply to the PIE News project; cases b) and especially c) apply instead to some data types, for which the opt-out option will therefore be chosen (see Sect. 2.2.4 of this document).

Given also the legal framework for privacy and data protection presented above, in what follows the strategy the PIE News project team adopts to manage data and to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (F.A.I.R.) is presented.

2. PIE NEWS DATA

Fig. 06

There are three main categories of data collection methods that the PIE News project employs:

1. **desk research** on existing data on socio-economic conditions and available welfare provisions in the three pilot countries.
2. **face-to-face research** and evaluation activities conducted primarily at pilot sites, and including interviews, focus groups and workshops;
3. **online research** and evaluation activities including online surveys, platform/web/social analytics, and users analytics.

Each type of data requires specific procedures related to both participants' privacy protection and data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction. The following sections address the peculiarities of each type of data.

2.1 DESK RESEARCH AND RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

2.1.1 Data origin

The project leverage on secondary analysis of statistic data and the collection of existing welfare state provisions in the three pilot countries (WP2 – see also D2.1, forthcoming at M9, March 2017).

As for Italy, BIN collected data that come from pre-existing literature (both Italian and international), Italian and European past and present laws and social protection policies (mainly through MISSOC), Italian draft laws [10], and statistical reports of the statistical office of the European Union (EUROSTAT), the Italian National Institute for Statistics (ISTAT), the European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC), the Bank of Italy, the Italian social security institute (INPS), the National Council for Economy and Work (CNEL), the Revenues Agency (Agenzia delle Entrate), and other relevant institutions such

as Confindustria, Caritas-Migrantes, SaveTheChildren, and UNICEF.

As for the Netherlands, SF collected data that come from Dutch and European past and present laws, pre-existing reports of the European Commission, the International Labour Organization, the Foundation of Labour, and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).

As for Croatia, CMS relied on both publicly available and not publicly available data. Publicly available data comes from a) pre-existing literature; b) national and European legislations; c) European and national statistical offices such as EUROSTAT, the United Nations Statistic Division, and the Croatian Bureau of Statistics. To the latter, CMS requested and obtained also data at the county level that are not publicly available; the same happened with the Hrvatska elektroprivreda (HEP Group), which is the national electricity service (see D6.1 – POPD – Requirement No. 1: Authorisations for not publicly available data, and D6.4 – POPD – Requirement No. 4: Publicly available existing data).

Further details on data sources for pilot activities will be provided in the Deliverable 2.1 – Research Report (M9).

Abertay University (AU) is also conducting online ethnography and online observations of public websites. The goal of this research is to observe existing best practices in relation to the design and use of online reputation so that if solutions that are deemed interesting for PIE News could be further studied and imported in the platform. Data is collected in an observational manner from several public websites and platforms using the browser as a sort of desktop-research. Data collection from online observation will respect the privacy of individuals and other relevant regulations (e.g., copyright of content). A list of the websites which is investigated with online observation will be provided in the Deliverable 3.1 – User Research Report and Scenarios.

2.1.2 Data collection purposes and its relation to the PIE News objectives

The aim is twofold. On the one hand, the objective is to understand the transformations of the socio-economic system and the welfare state model in Europe, and especially in the three pilot countries, and to obtain a clearer picture of the PIE conditions of the target groups (WP2). On the other hand, the information on available welfare provisions for each pilot country constitute the first brick of the Information Hub of the PIE News platform (WP4).

For what concerns online ethnography, the purpose is to study how other platform services and their reputation solutions work, with the goal to identify best practices that can be “imported” in PIE News.

2.1.3 Data types, formats, and expected size

Desk-research activities on existing socio-economic statistic data and welfare provisions generate the following:

- ▶ analytical report in the form of the Deliverable 2.1 Research Report, Ch. 2 (which may be the basis for further publications);
- ▶ Welfare Provision Sheets including a brief summary – an abstract – in English and the full description of the measure, complemented with relevant links (e.g., to the web space where the application form for the specific provision can be downloaded), in the language of the pilot country where the provision is in force.

The number of Welfare Provision Sheets depends on the number of welfare measures available in the three pilot countries. It is expected to run from 50 to 80.

Online ethnography produces screenshots stored as images; as this is a continuously ongoing activity, at the present moment the size of the dataset is not known.

2.1.4 Data utility and public availability

The above-mentioned data could be useful to academic researchers interested in topics such as life conditions and labour market, also from a comparative perspective. Data could be useful also for policy makers and other stakeholders to widen knowledge and to define more accurate and efficient course of actions.

Data will be made available in the following manner.

- ▶ The analytical report of D2.1 Research Report will be available as open publication freely downloadable on the project website and, later on, on Zenodo. Moreover, it will serve as a basis for the PIE News Factsheets, and for the statistics section of the Information Hub of the platform.

- ▶ Welfare Provision Sheets will be published on the Information Hub of the Platform (besides being part of the Deliverable 2.1 – Research Report, Sect. 2.1).

For what concerns online ethnography, the research team has not yet decided how or if to make this material available. The team will provide detailed new information on completion of the present deliverable as soon as the decision will be reached.

2.2 FACE-TO-FACE RESEARCH AND EVALUATION ACTIVITIES AT PILOT SITES

2.2.1 Data origin

The second category of data relates to face-to-face research and evaluation activities conducted by pilot partners (BIN Italy, Center for Peace Studies, Stitching Staff) within WP2 tasks; by Abertay University (AU) and Dyne.org, and the University of Trento (UNITN) within, respectively, WP3 and WP4 research activities; and possibly also by the Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute (M-ITI) within WP5 dissemination and public engagement activities. Especially, three data collection techniques are employed: (1) interviews, (2) focus groups, (3) workshops.

2.2.2 Data collection purposes and its relation to the PIE News objectives

Interviews and focus groups aim at gathering individual and collective narratives concerning the discussed topics, such as emerging needs in the target groups, non-institutional welfare measures (e.g., organized by grassroots movements, bottom-up initiatives), everyday practices to handle primary needs (e.g., household, nutrition, mobility), concepts of the future that may improve participants’ life conditions, as well as conceptions of trust and social capital that may influence reputation mechanisms (WP2 and WP3).

Workshops, including the four PIE News Design Workshops and other co-design and evaluation sessions organized at pilot sites, are collective meetings characterized by the production of artefacts, such as drawings, maps, lists, paper-pattern of interfaces, and the like. The focus rests on the way digital technologies – and the PIE News platform in particular – may (be designed to) improve participants’ life conditions (WP2, WP4 and WP5).

Data collected during the above sketched activities are at the core of the entire project. In fact, PIE News adopts a bottom-up, co-participatory design that foster people involvement to create the most efficient and the most effective platform. Gathering participants’ needs, opinions on digital technologies, and viewpoints on the future is paramount to reach the objectives of the PIE News project.

2.2.3 Data types, formats, and expected size

Data collected through research activities including interviews, focus groups and workshops consists of the following:

- ▶ questionnaires filled during interviews (either on digital support, or paper-based and then scanned), and a dataset with answers in aggregate form;
- ▶ photographs, audio- and/or video-recordings of the face-to-face activities;
- ▶ anonymised transcriptions (text files) of the audio-/video-recordings;
- ▶ artefacts that the participants and the researchers will co-produce during workshops, and
- ▶ their visual capturing/reproduction (e.g., photographs, scanned copies).

It is expected that each pilot partner will involve around 80 participants within the scope of WP2, thus collecting up to 240 filled questionnaires. Recordings of interviews and connected transcriptions will not surpass that number as well. To this, around 30 interviews conducted within the scope of WP3 are to be added. As for focus groups, each pilot partner is expected to organize 5 to 10 of them, which will amount to 15 to 30 recordings and related transcriptions. Finally, besides the 4 PIE News Design Workshops, it is difficult to estimate how many co-design and evaluation sessions will be organized at each pilot site, given that, to foster public engagement and the future sustainability of the platform, the project team intend to exploit any emerging opportunity and to realize as much meetings as possible.

2.2.4 Data utility and public availability

Data can be useful for academic researchers, NGO and private organizations, as well as for public offices who need to study and enhance their knowledge about citizens' life conditions, and the relationship between national welfare systems and their beneficiaries. Considered the general methodology adopted, related to bottom-up perspectives

and participatory design, also studies concerning innovative approaches can be carried on.

As detailed in Section 3.2, data from questionnaires in aggregate form and some visual materials co-produced during workshops will be made publicly accessible as Open Research Data (ORD) via Zenodo.

The original recordings and their transcription, and the original artefacts will not be made publicly available due, respectively, to privacy and data protection reasons, and to practical issues.

2.3 ONLINE RESEARCH AND EVALUATION ACTIVITIES

2.3.1 Data origin

The third category of data relates to online research and evaluation activities conducted by the University of Trento (UNITN), Abertay University (AU), Create-NET (CN), and the Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute (M-ITI) within WP3, WP4 and WP5. There are three main data gathering methods involved: (1) online survey, (2) platform/web/social analytics through several monitoring tools (see Sect. 2.3.3 for a list), (3) platform registered users profiling for analytics and service personalization.

2.3.2 Data collection purposes and its relation to the PIE News objectives

Online surveys fall primarily within the WP5 objectives, and aim (a) to engage, (b) to progressively monitor the engagement, and (c) to evaluate the dis/satisfaction of targeted participants. To reach the first and second objectives, an Early User Survey (EUS) has been conducted (see D5.1 – Evaluation Plan, Ch. 5); results will be compared with data coming from platform/web/social analytics to progressively evaluate engagement. As for the third objective, short User-Stakeholder Satisfaction Surveys are planned (see D5.1 – Evaluation Plan, Sect. 4.1).

Platform, web and social analytics have a threefold purpose: (a) to analyse the different patterns of interaction of PIE participants with and on the considered ICTs; (b)

Fig. 07

to understand participants' interests about the diverse information (sources) available on the PIE News online tools; and (c) to get to know how the different services offered by the platform are accessed and used (or not) by participants. These fall within the objectives of WP3, WP4 and WP5 in terms of, respectively, social capital and network dynamics analysis, public design, and evaluation. Anonymous aggregation of user choices and interface accessing will let the consortium know about the usage of the platform and is not providing a conflict with the personalized information provided.

In fact, users willing to register with the PIE News platform to become active members of the PIE News community, will provide some personal information (see below), and will allow to trace their preferred topics/activities on the platform. Such data will be used to further understanding of users' needs and their interactional dynamics on the platform (WP3), and to ameliorate the latter on such a basis (WP4, WP5). Profiling information about user activities will be maintained and recorded with the objective to offer users personalized services and recommendations about content that can match their specific interests.

At the present moment, the PIE News team cannot offer a detailed description of the information that will be collected. Given the bottom-up, co-design approach of the project through pilot activities and meetings with participants, the research team expects to discuss and define with them what information should be more useful and collected. As soon as this will be defined², the team will provide a detailed description on completion of the present deliverable. It is however possible to assess now that participants who register to the platform upon their understanding and acceptance of the legal and privacy terms (see D6.3 – POPD – Requirement No. 3, and D6.7 – H – Requirement No. 7 on informed consent procedures) will provide their e-mail address and country of residence to set up the account; furthermore, it is very likely that information about participants' occupational and educational levels will be collected.

2.3.3 Data types, formats, and expected size

Online surveys are instantiated through the open-source "Lime Survey" tool hosted by UNITN (a PIE News installation of Lime Survey hosted on the premises of the project technical partners is foreseen, see also D5.1 – Evaluation Plan, Sect. 5.1). For each survey, Lime Survey generates a statistical dataset with information at the individual level (each respondent is identified only by an ID number, so that privacy is assured). The EUS has collected 166 responses. Given their strict relation with pilot activities, it is difficult to estimate how many respondents the USSSs will gather. For this reason, it is at the present moment not possible to estimate the size of the datasets, as it is given by the number of respondents multiplied by the number of questions. The PIE News project team has however decided that the number of questions must be less than 16 in order to minimize the burden on participants. The research team also decided that only closed, multiple-choice questions are allowed to avoid ex-post codifications that may over-interpret answers.

To monitor the usage of the platform (commonfare.net), the PIE News team adopts the open-source analytics platform "Piwik", self-hosted by CN. Piwik is an open-source analytics platform that reports data such as visits, keywords, visitor locations and browsers. Data are displayed as tables, pie charts, bar graphs, tag clouds. It allows to export data in multiple formats: CSV, Excel, XML, JSON, PHP.

As on the institutional project website (pieproject.eu) no action by the visitor is required and, therefore, there is no sharing of personal information, the most cost-effective solution consisting in Google Analytics is adopted. In case of particular needs, also web logs will be analysed. Regarding the PieNewsCommonfare page on Facebook, both the Facebook Insights function and the Netvizz application [11] will be used. Netvizz is a tool that extracts data from different sections of the Facebook platform (groups, pages, search). It allows to export data in multiple formats: GDF for graph analysis, and spreadsheets applications and statistical packages to read tabular outputs.

Regarding #commonfare and #pienews, the Twitter analytics will be used to monitor the hashtag diffusion (plus other possible hashtag monitoring tools). Finally, YouTube analytics will be used for monitoring purposes with respect to the project videos uploaded on the YouTube channel.

All data acquired by the PIE News platform from the different online channels above mentioned, will be stored in servers controlled by Create-Net in its secured data centre infrastructure. Every data needed to be extracted for research and analysis purposes will be exported in an aggregated and anonymised form, using as standard export formats CSV and JSON.

2.3.4 Data utility and public availability

This type of data could be highly relevant for researchers interested in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI); co-design, participatory design and public design, particularly with respect to public engagement and the formation of a recursive public; network dynamics analysis (NDA); for scholars and NGOs interested in social policy, as platform analytics allow understanding what are people's needs; and for general as well as specialized press, that can disseminate research outputs within general public and professionals.

Data will be made available in anonymous and aggregated form as Open Research Data on Zenodo for research purposes only.

² The interface is being designed, the first release will be ready by the end of February 2017, in line with the project timeline. However, the project team expects to have users registering to the platform starting from the second release (September 2017), once pilot activities with participants will be advanced enough to support their engagement, and especially once the platform will have Stories Hub and Networking Hub fully operational. Only at that point it will make sense for users to register in order to share contents, interact with each other, and receive pie coins on the platform.

3. PIE NEWS F.A.I.R. DATA

Fig.08

TYPE	CODE/NAME	FORMAT	ACCESSIBILITY	AVAIL-ABILITY	DEPOSIT
(A) Face-to-face ques- tionnaires	PIE_QUEST_[pilot code]_[interview num- ber] (e.g., PIE_QUEST_ IT_001)	Paper-based or digital ques- tion- naires	Paper-based and XLSX file	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(B) Face-to-face ques- tionnaires scanned copies	PIE_QUEST_[pilot code]_[interview num- ber]_scan	Scanned copies	PDF files	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(C) Face-to-face ques- tionnaires dataset	PIE_QUEST_[pilot code]_AGG_CC	Dataset aggregate form	XLSX and SAV files	Open	Zenodo
(D) Interviews tran- scriptions	PIE_INT-txt_[pilot code]_[interview num- ber]	Transcrip- tions	PDF files	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(E) Audio and video recordings of interviews	PIE_INT-aud_[pilot code]_[interview num- ber], PIE_INT-vid_[pi- lot code]_[interview number]	Audio- and video-re- cordings	MP3, WMA, AVI, MP4, M4V, MOV, WAV, DIVX, MPEG, MKV files	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(F) Focus groups tran- scriptions	PIE_FOCUS-txt_[pilot code]_[focus number]	Transcrip- tions	PDF files	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(G) Audio and video recordings of focus groups	PIE_FOCUS-aud_[pilot code]_[focus number], PIE_FOCUS-vid_[pilot code]_[focus number]	Audio- and video-re- cordings	MP3, WMA, AVI, MP4, M4V, MOV, WAV, DIVX, MPEG, MKV files	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(H) Workshops tran- scriptions	PIE_WS-txt_[pilot code]_[workshop num- ber]	Transcrip- tions	PDF files	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(I) Audio and video recordings of workshops	PIE_WS-aud, PIE_WS- vid_[pilot code]_[work- shop number]	Audio- and video-re- cordings	MP3, WMA, AVI, MP4, M4V, MOV, WAV, DIVX, MPEG, MKV files	Restricted	Relevant WP leaders
(J) Artefacts	PIE_WS-vis_[pilot code]_[workshop num- ber]_CC	Visual capturing/ represen- tation of paper-based artefacts	PDF files	Open	Zenodo

(K) Online early user survey	PIE_EUS_AGG	Dataset	XLSX and SAV files	Restricted	Create-net
(L) Online user stakeholders satisfaction survey	PIE_USSS_AGG	Dataset	XLSX and SAV files	Restricted	Create-net
(M) Platform/web/social analytics	PIE_NDA-PLA_AGG_CC, PIE_NDA-WEB_AGG_CC, PIE_NDA-FB_AGG_CC, PIE_NDA-#, PIE_NDA-YT_AGG_CC	Tables, pie charts, bar graphs, tag clouds	CSV, XLSX, SAV, XML, JSON, PHP, GDF, tabular outputs	Open	Create-net and Zenodo
(N) Users log	PIE_LOG_AGG_CC	Tables, pie charts, bar graphs, tag clouds	CSV AND JSON	Open	Create-net and Zenodo

TABLE 1: DATA SUMMARY

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

The PIE News team members will share data via Zenodo, the research data repository developed by CERN within the EU OpenAIRE project. Shared data will be mentioned on the project website, in the Resources section, and will be complemented with the link to the relevant document on Zenodo.

Zenodo assigns all publicly available uploads a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make the upload easily and uniquely citeable. Zenodo further supports harvesting of all content via the OAI-PMH protocol.

Each dataset has an identifier, a code which is also the prefix of the name of each file contained into that specific dataset. All dataset codes start with “PIE”, followed by an underscore, and continue with the proper dataset identifier, such as “QUEST” for the questionnaires, “INT” for the interviews, etc. (see Table 1 for the full list). For some datasets, the identifier is followed, after a dash, by the format code, such as “txt” or “aud”, for text (transcription) and “audio” respectively. Moreover, datasets concerning pilot activities continue, after an underscore, with the pilot country code (“HR” or “IT” or “NL”). Each file is named with the dataset code followed, after an underscore, either by the progressive number of the file in the dataset, or by the label “AGG” when data are shared only in their aggregate form. Files in the respective dataset are numbered with three or four digits depending on the dataset size. Finally, the label “CC”, referring to the licensing, is added for data released with Creative Commons license (see Sect. 3.4). As detailed in Sections 2.2.4 and 3.2, single questionnaires and single transcriptions will not be made publicly available via Zenodo, but the datasets containing them will be prepared anyway and made accessible on request. Examples of names are: “PIE_INT-txt_HR_001”, “PIE_QUEST_NL_AGG_CC”.

A similar procedure is adopted for publications and deliverables. All publication codes start with “PIE”, followed by an underscore, and continue with authors’ names followed by another underscore, then the year of publication,

followed by an underscore, then the title of the publications, followed by an underscore, and it ends with “CC”, referring to the licensing: “PIE_[Author/s]_[year]_[title]_CC”.

All deliverable codes start with PIE, followed by an underscore. Then they continue with the letter D (that means “deliverable”), immediately followed by the WP number the deliverable belongs to, followed by a dot, then by the number of the deliverable, and lastly by an underscore. The code continues with the letter V (that means “version”), immediately followed by a number identifying the version, then by a dot, and then by a number that identifies minor changes. Alternatively, the version number is replaced by “FIN” (deliverables uploaded on the Participant Portal). After another underscore, the code ends with “CC”, referring to the licensing (deliverables uploaded on Zenodo). An example of file name is therefore “PIE_Dx.x_Vx.x_CC”, another is “PIE_Dx.x_FIN_CC”.

Each file uploaded into Zenodo can be found not only through keywords related to the project (such as PIE, poverty, income, (un)employment), but also through specific keywords for each file depending on the content. Therefore, data coming from face-to-face activities will come with keywords such as welfare, trust and social capital. Data from online research and evaluation activities will include keywords such as networks, social media, and HCI.

The PIE News research team does not expect to share updated versions of data, but if this will be the case, versioning will be simplified by numbering file versions in succession, as explained above concerning deliverables (e.g., 1.0, 2.0, etc.).

The PIE News team members will adopt the best practice for the assignment of metadata as developed within Zenodo. Metadata is licensed under CCO, except for email addresses. All metadata is exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested. All metadata is stored internally in MARC according to the schema defined in <http://inveniosoftware.org/wiki/Project/OpenAIREplus/DevelopmentRecordMarkup>. Metadata is exported in several standard formats such as MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema

according to OpenAIRE Guidelines.

Given the interdisciplinary nature of the PIE News project, the research team aims at choosing the standard of metadata that is more suitable for each discipline simultaneously to improve interoperability and make data finding easier. The PIE News research team expects to define the standard of metadata when more information will be gathered about the data that are needed, for example after the preliminary analysis of EUS data.

For textual items, English is preferred but also Italian, Dutch, and Croatian are accepted.

3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

The PIE News members will collect only personal but not sensitive data. Personal data will not be openly accessible, nor available to third parties to guarantee participants' privacy.

More specifically, with respect to face-to-face research activities, the following data will be made publicly available:

- ▶ data from questionnaires in aggregate form;
- ▶ visual capturing/reproduction (e.g., photographs) of the artefacts that the participants and the researchers will co-produce during workshops.

All these will be made available as single PDF files, accessible through manifold software applications.

It is however necessary to declare that visual materials including personal data or personal images that can endanger participants' privacy will not be made publicly available. The original recordings and artefacts will not be made publicly available due, respectively, to personal data protection reasons, and to practical issues. Both single questionnaires and single transcriptions will not be made publicly accessible as Open Research Data (ORD). Transcriptions and questionnaires will be stored on secure space by relevant WP leaders (e.g., AU for interviews within WP3 tasks, BIN for pilot activities within WP2). The rationale

for this decision concerns participants' identification, as the amount of information that the considered data contain can allow others to identify single participants. For publications, data from questionnaires will be used only in aggregate form, and only short excerpts of interviews/focus groups/workshops will be cited.

As for transcriptions and any other data that may allow the identification of participants, the PIE News research team will decide case-by-case, also with the help of the Internal Ethical Board and/or other Ethics Committees if needed, whether to make accessible the data or not. The research team will consider several aspects, such as the coherence between the data and the applicants' aim, applicants' reputation, and applicants' ethical standards. Overall, the PIE News research team will evaluate the purpose and intended use of the data and then decide whether to provide an anonymous copy, in compliance with the ethical standards defined in this Data Management Plan and in the deliverables answering ethics requirements (WP6).

As for online research, the following will be made openly available via Zenodo:

- ▶ online survey output (EUS/USSS) gained via Lime Survey and shared as Excel and SPSS file;
- ▶ platform/web/social analytics gained via Piwik for the platform, Google Analytics for the website, Facebook Insights and Netvizz for the Facebook page, Twitter analytics for hashtags diffusion, and YouTube analytics for the YouTube channel; these data are accessible as CSV, Excel, XML, JSON, PHP, and GDF files;
- ▶ user analytics/log gained via Google Analytics and shared as GDF, Excel, and SPSS files.

In any case, personal data, such as names and e-mail addresses, will not be made publicly available for protecting users' privacy.

The file containing information linking data, metadata, documentation and codes will be stored securely into the Zenodo repository, maintained by CERN (see also Chapter 4 "Data security").

Fig. 09

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

As mentioned in Section 3.1, the PIE News project has an interdisciplinary nature so both metadata and interoperability choices will be chosen to improve connection among different disciplines. However, given the bottom-up, participatory design approach, the research team is not able at the present moment to specify (the content of) all the data that will be collected; hence, more detailed information about interoperability will be provided on completion of the present deliverable. The research team has however already agreed that syntactic and semantic interoperability is assured by using (where pertinent) the XML and SQL standards, the ASCII/UNICODE standards, and as for data the most common file formats so that they can be handled with the most widely and frequently used analytical software.

3.4 INCREASING DATA RE-USE: LICENSES

To foster the widest possible reuse, the PIE News team adopts the Creative Common License International 4.0 BY-NC-SA for its data. The CC-BY-NC-SA license allows others to copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format under the following terms:

- ▶ others must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. Others may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses them;
- ▶ others may not use the material for commercial purposes;
- ▶ if others remix, transform, or build upon the original material, they can distribute the modified material, but
- ▶ others license their new creations under the identical terms.

All the clauses NC-SA-ND allow reuse but there are good reasons to hold NC (to avoid unauthorized commercial exploitation of our work and of information people shared with us) and SA (to have growing commons of data, on the model of the GNU GPL).

For publications, BY-NC-SA-ND licensing is possible, if the authors do not want their work to be circulated in different forms than the published one.

Data will be available as Open Research Data no later than two months after the end of the project. Nor embargo status neither restricted access will apply.

For what concerns data quality, all information is provided “as-is”, and the user shall hold Zenodo and information providers supplying data to Zenodo free and harmless in connection with the use of such information.

3.5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Zenodo is free so any additional costs for its usage is expected. Data will be uploaded by CN as Technical Coordinator (see T1.3 of the project proposal) and as part of WP5 dissemination activities, therefore with the support of M-ITI (see T5.2, sub 3) of the project proposal). More specifically, deliverables and publications will be uploaded no later than 3 months after release, whereas datasets will be uploaded at the end of the project, within 3 months by the closing of project activities (M36).

Each WP is responsible for preparing the datasets to make FAIR the data collected within its own activities, provided that UNITN, as Project Coordinator, and CN, as Technical Coordinator (see WP1 – Project Management) are co-responsible for general coordination and supervision. At least one responsible person from each WP involved in data collection activities (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5) will be selected, together with a data management supervisor from UNITN and CN. It is up to the WP leader to decide whether to select only one responsible for the WP or one responsible for each partner organization involved in the WP. Responsible persons will be selected by the end of January 2017 (M7).

A long-term preservation of data is highly desirable because it will allow further analysis, also in comparative and longitudinal perspectives. The static hosting of collections of data imposes very little overhead while granting the long term availability of it. Data that is of public interest will be made available on the file download zone of DYNE and other partners. Whenever freezing the collections the use of open protocols will be preferred.

4. DATA SECURITY

Fig. 10

The aim of this chapter is to present and discuss the issues related to the treatment of the collected data in electronic form, their storage, and their distribution using network connections.

The pilot activities and the utilization of the PIE News platform from the end users' perspective requires the collection and storage of personal data. The consortium guarantees that all personal data collected during the project will be kept secure and unreachable by unauthorized persons. The data will be handled with appropriate confidentiality, accessibility controls, and technical security. The platform will use a number of security policies and rules to ensure the integrity and availability of electronic information captured, stored, maintained, and used.

The PIE News team will store **research data** on secure repositories protected by password at the head offices of partner organizations. File names will not make reference to any personal information. Information that might enable data to be linked to individuals, such as the file linking participants' names to their respective code/pseudonym, will be password protected and encrypted so that access will be restricted to only those with the requisite credentials.

The PIE News **platform** will be hosted on a secure data centre infrastructure, controlled by the Technical Coordinator (CREATE-NET), that can share backups of public assets produced by the project (software and data) with other partners willing to preserve them and maintain them even beyond the span of the project. To assure the participants' privacy, any identifiable data will be anonymised and encrypted prior to storage. Access to this data is restricted to the researchers involved in the project considering the data protection guidelines in this document.

More specifically the server onto which the data will be stored will have **server side encryption**, adopting the standard GNU/Linux hard-disk encryption using LUKS, which is compliant with ISO/IEC 18033-3:2010, namely AES128 or 256 bit block cipher encryption. That means that the server's administration personnel will be able to generate public keys for specific personnel who will have

access to the data but will not be able to access the data themselves (since the private keys required for this access will be generated on the machine of the person with access to the data). That means that only the required personnel will have access to the data and even in the remote case of a possible data leak or server hack the data stolen will be fully encrypted and thus fully non-accessible.

The protection of personal data will be also ensured through the use of HTTPS protocol for the encryption of all internet transactions, and appropriate European and Internet security **standards** from ISO, ITU, W3C, IETF and ETSI. The platform will also provide additional security mechanisms to protect data and eliminate risks such as SQL injection, Cross-site scripting (XSS) and session hijacking. Furthermore, the platform will support secure protocols (SSL) and encryption mechanisms to allow the secure transmission of sensitive information over the network. Data protection is enhanced by self-hosted open-source solutions and architecture.

Registered user profiles will be stored in the platform server, deployed at a data centre controlled by the TC, and accessible only by authorized personnel. No passwords will be stored (only hashes) and therefore the personal profile information (including email, country of residence and preferred topics/activities on the platform) will be only accessible by the registered user. User registration, authentication and data access will be implemented according to state of the art security practices and standards. The platform will provide **authentication mechanisms** and policies to assure authorized access to the platform's data; the generation, maintenance and transmission of strong passwords. It will provide User Access Control mechanisms that give the right privileges to the platform users.

In the case of social media content, no encryption takes place since there is significant computational overhead in encrypting large amounts of dynamic data, which makes it impractical for social media content. However, the data is stored on a secure server with access possible only to authorized personnel.

In terms of **restricted access**, authorized researchers from

partner organizations, from the PIE News Internal Ethical Board, from the Ethical Committee of the University of Trento, Abertay University and CREATE-NET, and from the competent Authority can access collected data and research results, even if at an intermediary stage. In the general case, the “raw” data related to the participants to the project, will be handled only by the research team involved in the WPs that entails activities with the participants, and made available to the rest of the consortium only in anonymous and/or aggregated form.

For what concerns Open Research Data, the research outputs are stored safely for the future on Zenodo, in same cloud infrastructure as research data from CERN's Large Hadron Collider and using CERN's battle-tested repository software INVENIO, which is used by some of the

world's largest repositories such as INSPIRE HEP and CERN Document Server. Data is stored in CERN Data Center. Both data files and metadata are kept in multiple online replicas and independent replicas. CERN has considerable knowledge and experience in building and operating large scale digital repositories and a commitment to maintain this data centre to collect and store 100s of PBs of LHC data as it grows over the next 20 years. In the highly unlikely event that Zenodo will have to close operations, all content will be migrated to other suitable repositories, and since all uploads have DOIs, all citations and links to Zenodo resources will not be affected.

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

All activities will be carried out ensuring the ethical principles and in compliance with Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and subsequent Regulation 2016/679/EC and Directive 2016/680/EC, about the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, as well as Directive 2002/58/EC, concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector, as modified by Directive 2009/136/EC. All national data protection and privacy laws for pilot countries will be also followed.

Copies of ethical approvals for the collection of personal data by Ethical Boards are contained in the Deliverable 6.6 – POPD – Requirement No. 6: Ethical approvals. As described in the DoA, Section 5.1: Ethics (see p. 192 of the GA),

the partner organizations who have an Ethical Board are going to get ethical approval and the terms of approval will constitute the basis of the detailed ethical guidelines that will be included in the Project Management Handbook (D1.1, M3). The guidelines included in the Project Management Handbook will apply to the whole consortium.

As stated in the Deliverable 6.2 – POPD – Requirement No. 2: **Sensitive** Data, no sensitive personal data will be collected nor processed within the PIE News project activities. **Personal** but not sensitive data will be collected and managed in the manner described in the documents submitted for ethics review, in the Chapter 5 of the Deliverable 1.1 – Project Handbook, and in the Deliverable 6.5 – POPD – Requirement No. 5: Data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction.

As detailed in the deliverables D6.3 – POPD – Requirement No. 3 and D6.7 – H – Requirement No. 7 on **informed consent** procedures (see also D1.1 – Project Handbook, Ch. 5), participants will be informed before the beginning of activities about the project objectives, the treatment of personal data, and where additional information can be sought. Depending on the research method involved, either (a) an Information Sheet will be provided to each participant, who will be then asked to sign an Informed Consent Form (see the English templates of the two documents in the appendixes of the above-mentioned deliverables), or (b) the Terms of service will be available to users, and an agreement will be asked (i)

to all users concerning cookies and (ii) to registering users concerning also personal data treatment.

As described in the Chapter 5 of the Deliverable 1.1 – Project Handbook, and also in the Deliverable 6.8 – POPD – Requirement No. 8: Preventing the risk of enhancing vulnerability/stigmatisation, participants' **anonymity and confidentiality** will be guaranteed with respect to all the research activities carried out and data gathered. Following the best practice for ethics in Human-Computer Interaction [12], any personal (but not sensitive) data collected will be anonymised. Personal information and details will be never released in forms that might make participants identifiable to any extent. Anonymization will take place through pseudonymisation, generalization, and any other reasonably employable mean.

Data collected via all online tools that PIE News project uses for research and evaluation activities is always performed avoiding to collect any personal data of users, with the following unique exception: in the case of users willing to register, the PIE News platform will maintain and record profiling information about user activities with the objective to offer them personalized services and recommendations. As mentioned above, before registering to the PIE News platform, these users will be asked to accept terms and conditions explicating what kind of data, type of processing and purpose of usage of this data in order to gain from them an informed consent about their registration and participation to the PIE News platform activities. In all other cases, such as anonymous/unregistered users accessing the PIE News platform and participation to online surveys, all data will be collected, by design, in an anonymised way to avoid to store any data that can be connected to any user getting in contact with PIE News online tools. Also in the case of social platforms, like Facebook and YouTube, all data collected via analytics tools offered by these platforms will be collected in an aggregated and anonymised way, avoiding to acquire, by design, any personal data related to interested users. For what pertains to analytics exported and shared externally to the project, all exported data will be based on anonymously classified and logged data (age, gender, etc.) which is not related with the personalized profile or preference of the user.

REFERENCES

- [1] Directive 95/46/EC of 24 October 1995 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX-31995L0046:EN:NOT>) on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, Official Journal L 281, 23/11/1995 p. 31-50.
- [2] Directive 2002/58/EC of 12 July 2002 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX-32002L0058:en:HTML>) concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications), Official Journal. L 201, 31/7/2002 p. 37-47.
- [3] Directive 2009/136/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2009 amending Directive 2002/22/EC on universal service and users' rights relating to electronic communications networks and services, Directive 2002/58/EC concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector and Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004 on cooperation between national authorities responsible for the enforcement of consumer protection laws (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:337:0011:0036:en:PDF>)
- [4] Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (general data protection regulation), Official Journal L119, 04/05/2016, p. 1-88.
- [5] Directive 2016/680/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016L0680&from=EN>) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing council framework decision 2008/977/JHA, Official Journal L 119, 04/05/2016, p. 89-131.
- [6] Council Framework Decision 2005/222/JHA of the European Parliament of 24 February 2005 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32005F0222&from=EN>) on attacks against information systems, Official Journal L 69, 17/03/2005, p. 67-71.
- [7] Directive 2013/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 August 2013 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013L0040&from=EN>) on attacks against information systems and replacing Council Framework Decision 2005/222/JHA, Official Journal L 218, 14.08.2013, p. 8-14.
- [8] H2020 Programme Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020, European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf, 29 November 2016.
- [9] European Parliament legislative resolution of 12 March 2014 on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation), European Parliament.
- [10] Disegni di legge nn. 2494, 2241 e 2437 – Contrasto alla povertà e riordino delle prestazioni sociali, XI Commissione “Lavoro, previdenza sociale” del Senato della Repubblica, Roma, 8 novembre 2016. Audizione del Presidente dell'Istituto nazionale di statistica Giorgio Allewa: <http://www.istat.it/it/archivio/192391>
- [11] Bernhard Rieder (2013). Studying Facebook via Data Extraction: The Netvizz Application. WebSci'13, May 2–4, 2013, Paris, France. http://rieder.polsys.net/files/rieder_websci.pdf.
- [12] Minocha, Shailey and Tzanidou, Ekaterini (2010). Ethics in usability engineering. In: India HCI 2010/Interaction Design for International Development, 20-24 March 2010, Industrial Design Centre, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, Mumbai, India.